

Supplementary Material

for

“Combining optical and radio science data from JUICE and Europa Clipper missions to constrain the ephemerides of Io”

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Overview

This document provides additional theoretical derivations, implementation details, extended experiments, and supplementary figures supporting the main article.

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S1 Pinhole Camera Model

The approach adopted in the geometrical and mathematical analysis of the uncertainties is the pinhole camera, which is a simple geometric model to describe how a camera forms an image of a 3D scene onto a 2D image plane (Figure S1). All light-arrays are imagined to converge and pass through the pinhole of the camera, projecting an inverted image onto the opposite side (detector). The detector is the actual physical device (image sensor) that captures the image and it is positioned at a distance equal to the focal length f from the pinhole, along the line-of-sight.

A camera-fixed reference frame could be imagined to have z axis directed along the line-of-sight, while x and y axis are parallel to the lati of the detector.

The assumption introduced in the analysis is that the z axis always points directly towards Io at instants where images are taken, meaning Io centroid will always be more or less at the center of the detector.

In the case of JANUS, it utilizes a CMOS (Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor) image sensor of 2000×1504 pixels of size $7 \mu m$. The focal length is $f = 467 mm$ while the FOV is $1.72^\circ \times 1.29^\circ$.

If we define $FOV_x = 1.72$, $FOV_y = 1.29$, 2000 pixels along x and 1504 pixels along y , the pixel angular resolution, i.e. the angle subtended by a single pixel, is then equal to:

$$pixel_ang_res = \frac{FOV_x}{2000} = \frac{FOV_y}{1504} = 8.59e - 4 \frac{deg}{pixel} \quad (S1)$$

Also Europa Clipper NAC camera uses a CMOS sensor, but in this case its size is 2048×4096 pixels of size $10 \mu m$. The focal length is $f = 1000 mm$ and the FOV is $1.17^\circ \times 2.35^\circ$. In this case, defining $FOV_x = 1.17$, $FOV_y = 2.35$, 2048 pixels along x and 4096 pixels along y , the pixel angular resolution is:

$$pixel_ang_res = \frac{FOV_x}{2048} = \frac{FOV_y}{4096} = 5.73e - 4 \frac{deg}{pixel} \quad (S2)$$

Figure S1: Pinhole camera model

The pinhole camera model allows for an easy computation of useful parameters, such as:

- Apparent diameter of the moon on the detector:

$$d_a[mm] = 2 \cdot R_{IO} \cdot \left(\frac{f}{D}\right); \quad (S3)$$

$$d_a[pixels] = d_a[mm] \cdot pixel_size[mm/pixel], \quad (S4)$$

where D is the moon-camera distance.

- Fraction of FOV occupied:

$$\frac{FOV_{occupied}}{FOV} = \frac{2}{FOV} \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{R_{IO}}{D}\right) \quad (S5)$$

S2 Constraints

In Table S1 are reported all the constraints used in the preliminary analysis to retrieve the allowable time windows for optical observations within each arc and revolution of JUICE and Europa Clipper missions.

Parameter	Value
Covered time span	1G01 to 27C21 for JUICE E001 to E053 for Europa Clipper
Start of ARC	24 hours before CA
End of ARC	24 hours after CA
Time around C/A without optnavs	± 12 h
Minimum Sun-spacecraft-Moon angle (Sun exclusion angle)	30°
Maximum Sun-Moon-spacecraft angle (Phase angle)	130°
Minimum Jupiter Limb-spacecraft-Moon angle (Jupiter Limb exclusion angle)	Jupiter limb always outside FOV
Minimum number of pixels to be filled by moon image (in one dimension)	5
Maximum fraction of the FOV that is allowed be filled by the Moon (in one dimension)	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}$

Table S1: Constraints used to define allowable epochs for optical observations

S3 Allowable Time Windows (TWs)

To provide a quantitative idea of the time reduction coming from the introduction of the constraints showed in Section S2, in Table S2 is summarized, for each JUICE arc, the reduction in the total available time for optical observations and the final TWs found. In Table S3, on the other hand, are summarized the data for the Europa Clipper mission arcs.

Arc	TWs after Sun Exclusion (Loss %)	TWs after Jup. Exclusion (Loss %)	Time windows (Start to End)
G01	24 hr (0%)	19.55 hr (18.53%)	[12/02/2032 23:07:00 to 12/02/2032 23:24:24] [13/02/2032 03:51:13 to 13/02/2032 11:06:59] [14/02/2032 11:07:00 to 14/02/2032 23:06:59]
G02	24 hr (0%)	14.40 hr (40.00%)	[10/04/2032 04:20:00 to 10/04/2032 13:42:35] [10/04/2032 16:11:16 to 10/04/2032 16:19:59] [11/04/2032 16:20:00 to 11/04/2032 18:44:02] [12/04/2032 01:51:12 to 12/04/2032 04:19:59]
G03	12 hr (50%)	9.40 hr (60.02%)	[01/06/2032 21:34:00 to 02/06/2032 06:57:44]
C01	0 hr (100%)	0 hr (100%)	NO TIME LEFT FOR THIS ARC!
E01	12 hr (50%)	6.26 hr (73.91%)	[01/07/2032 16:25:00 to 01/07/2032 18:26:51] [02/07/2032 00:11:09 to 02/07/2032 04:24:59]
E02	12 hr (50%)	6.88 hr (71.33%)	[16/07/2032 03:27:07 to 16/07/2032 10:19:59]
C02	24 hr (0%)	18.35 hr (23.12%)	[28/07/2032 05:06:45 to 28/07/2032 14:07:43] [29/07/2032 14:07:44 to 29/07/2032 23:27:51]
C03	24 hr (0%)	21.12 hr (12.02%)	[13/08/2032 18:31:30 to 13/08/2032 20:58:26] [13/08/2032 23:51:27 to 14/08/2032 06:31:29] [15/08/2032 06:31:30 to 15/08/2032 18:31:29]
C04	0.93 hr (96.13%)	0.93 hr (96.13%)	[09/09/2032 19:25:00 to 09/09/2032 20:20:40]
C05	12 hr (50%)	12.00 hr (50.00%)	[26/09/2032 11:59:00 to 26/09/2032 23:58:59]
C06	5.19 hr (78.38%)	1.35 hr (94.39%)	[13/10/2032 08:17:30 to 13/10/2032 09:38:15]
C07	12 hr (50%)	9.99 hr (58.38%)	[29/10/2032 20:50:00 to 30/10/2032 00:55:00] [30/10/2032 02:55:40 to 30/10/2032 08:49:59]
C08	10.53 hr (56.13%)	6.59 hr (72.54%)	[15/11/2032 13:13:00 to 15/11/2032 19:48:20]
C09	2.45 hr (89.79%)	1.21 hr (94.96%)	[02/12/2032 15:06:27 to 02/12/2032 16:19:02]
C10	12 hr (50%)	11.12 hr (53.68%)	[23/02/2033 16:06:07 to 23/02/2033 19:58:54] [23/02/2033 20:51:58 to 24/02/2033 04:06:06]
C11	19.92 hr (17%)	16.15 hr (32.29%)	[12/03/2033 08:29:00 to 12/03/2033 14:04:40] [12/03/2033 17:50:32 to 12/03/2033 20:28:59] [13/03/2033 20:29:00 to 14/03/2033 04:23:58]
C12	24 hr (0%)	21.60 hr (10.00%)	[09/05/2033 16:08:00 to 10/05/2033 00:04:31] [10/05/2033 02:28:33 to 10/05/2033 04:07:59] [11/05/2033 04:08:00 to 11/05/2033 16:07:59]
C13	20.71 hr (13.71%)	19.21 hr (19.96%)	[03/06/2033 20:00:50 to 04/06/2033 06:36:59] [05/06/2033 06:37:00 to 05/06/2033 15:13:21]
C14	12 hr (50%)	11.44 hr (52.33%)	[20/06/2033 11:01:00 to 20/06/2033 14:10:37] [20/06/2033 14:43:56 to 20/06/2033 23:00:59]
C15	24 hr (0%)	20.04 hr (16.50%)	[07/07/2033 03:23:00 to 07/07/2033 07:58:43] [07/07/2033 11:56:19 to 07/07/2033 15:22:59] [08/07/2033 15:23:00 to 09/07/2033 03:22:59]
C16	14.31 hr (40.38%)	11.93 hr (50.29%)	[23/07/2033 19:45:00 to 24/07/2033 04:34:07] [24/07/2033 06:56:40 to 24/07/2033 07:44:59] [25/07/2033 07:45:00 to 25/07/2033 10:03:33]
C17	24 hr (0%)	21.06 hr (12.27%)	[09/08/2033 12:13:00 to 09/08/2033 23:09:13] [11/08/2033 02:05:19 to 11/08/2033 12:12:59]
C18	24 hr (0%)	19.55 hr (18.55%)	[31/10/2033 22:58:00 to 01/11/2033 01:31:56] [01/11/2033 05:59:00 to 01/11/2033 10:57:59] [02/11/2033 10:58:00 to 02/11/2033 22:57:59]

Arc	TWs after Sun Esclusion (Loss %)	TWs after Jup. Esclusion (Loss %)	Time windows (Start to End)
G04	24 hr (0%)	24.00 hr (0.00%)	[26/11/2033 06:22:00 to 26/11/2033 18:21:59] [27/11/2033 18:22:00 to 28/11/2033 06:21:59]
C19	0 hr (100%)	0 hr (100%)	NO TIME LEFT FOR THIS ARC!
C20	24 hr (0%)	21.32 hr (11.13%)	[30/04/2034 22:17:49 to 01/05/2034 04:17:29] [01/05/2034 06:58:23 to 01/05/2034 10:17:48] [02/05/2034 10:17:49 to 02/05/2034 22:17:48]
C21	24 hr (0%)	21.24 hr (11.48%)	[23/06/2034 04:20:36 to 23/06/2034 14:51:30] [24/06/2034 17:36:51 to 25/06/2034 04:20:35]

Table S2: Observation Time Windows (TWs) for JUICE Arcs

Arc	TWs after Sun Esclusion (Loss %)	TWs after Jup. Esclusion (Loss %)	Time windows (Start to End)
E001	24 hr (0%)	20.42 hr (14.93%)	[06/03/2031 02:40:07 to 06/03/2031 11:05:04] [07/03/2031 14:40:07 to 08/03/2031 02:40:04]
E002	24 hr (0%)	12.79 hr (46.71%)	[26/03/2031 15:52:21 to 27/03/2031 02:06:12] [28/03/2031 02:06:15 to 28/03/2031 02:43:50] [28/03/2031 12:10:14 to 28/03/2031 14:06:12]
E003	24 hr (0%)	16.07 hr (33.04%)	[26/05/2031 12:58:44 to 26/05/2031 18:15:20] [28/05/2031 00:58:44 to 28/05/2031 11:46:32]
E004	24 hr (0%)	15.49 hr (35.46%)	[16/06/2031 20:06:11 to 16/06/2031 22:34:15] [17/06/2031 04:55:56 to 17/06/2031 08:06:08] [18/06/2031 08:06:11 to 18/06/2031 17:06:25] [18/06/2031 19:15:25 to 18/06/2031 20:06:08]
E005	24 hr (0%)	16.43 hr (31.54%)	[08/07/2031 03:13:37 to 08/07/2031 03:51:23] [08/07/2031 09:36:51 to 08/07/2031 15:13:34] [09/07/2031 15:13:37 to 09/07/2031 22:38:31] [10/07/2031 00:26:59 to 10/07/2031 03:13:34]
E006	24 hr (0%)	18.37 hr (23.46%)	[29/07/2031 14:42:28 to 29/07/2031 22:40:26] [30/07/2031 22:40:29 to 31/07/2031 04:01:19] [31/07/2031 05:36:52 to 31/07/2031 10:40:26]
E007	24 hr (0%)	20.24 hr (15.67%)	[19/08/2031 20:07:02 to 20/08/2031 06:08:25] [21/08/2031 06:08:28 to 21/08/2031 08:56:10] [21/08/2031 10:43:16 to 21/08/2031 18:08:25]
E008	24 hr (0%)	22.16 hr (7.67%)	[10/09/2031 01:37:18 to 10/09/2031 13:36:59] [11/09/2031 15:26:49 to 12/09/2031 01:36:59]
E009	24 hr (0%)	24 hr (0%)	[01/10/2031 09:07:24 to 01/10/2031 21:07:24] [02/10/2031 21:07:24 to 03/10/2031 09:07:24]
E010	24 hr (0%)	24 hr (0%)	[22/10/2031 21:44:28 to 23/10/2031 09:44:28] [24/10/2031 09:44:28 to 24/10/2031 21:44:28]
E011	24 hr (0%)	24 hr (0%)	[13/11/2031 05:15:22 to 13/11/2031 17:15:22] [14/11/2031 17:15:22 to 15/11/2031 05:15:22]
E012	24 hr (0%)	22.91 hr (4.54%)	[04/12/2031 12:54:49 to 04/12/2031 23:49:10] [06/12/2031 00:54:49 to 06/12/2031 12:54:46]
E013	24 hr (0%)	18.08 hr (24.67%)	[19/01/2032 16:43:49 to 19/01/2032 21:44:01] [19/01/2032 23:46:16 to 20/01/2032 04:43:46] [21/01/2032 04:43:49 to 21/01/2032 12:50:50]
E014	24 hr (0%)	16.04 hr (33.17%)	[10/02/2032 00:21:09 to 10/02/2032 02:58:04] [10/02/2032 05:02:58 to 10/02/2032 12:21:06] [11/02/2032 12:21:09 to 11/02/2032 17:48:58] [11/02/2032 23:41:29 to 12/02/2032 00:21:06]

Arc	TWs after Sun Exclusion (Loss %)	TWs after Jup. Exclusion (Loss %)	Time windows (Start to End)
E015	24 hr (0%)	15.19 hr (36.71%)	[02/03/2032 07:49:51 to 02/03/2032 08:04:33] [02/03/2032 10:26:54 to 02/03/2032 19:49:48] [03/03/2032 19:49:51 to 03/03/2032 22:14:08] [04/03/2032 04:40:07 to 04/03/2032 07:49:48]
E016	24 hr (0%)	18.04 hr (24.83%)	[23/03/2032 15:49:08 to 24/03/2032 03:49:07] [25/03/2032 09:46:54 to 25/03/2032 15:49:05]
E017	24 hr (0%)	20.89 hr (12.96%)	[10/04/2032 10:44:33 to 10/04/2032 22:44:30] [12/04/2032 01:51:21 to 12/04/2032 10:44:30]
E018	16.66 hr (30.58%)	16.66 hr (30.58%)	[24/04/2032 23:55:53 to 25/04/2032 11:55:50] [26/04/2032 11:55:53 to 26/04/2032 16:35:22]
E019	18.94 hr (21.08%)	18.94 hr (21.08%)	[12/05/2032 13:37:07 to 13/05/2032 01:37:07] [14/05/2032 01:37:07 to 14/05/2032 08:33:40]
E020	12 hr (50%)	6.16 hr (74.33%)	[27/05/2032 02:35:46 to 27/05/2032 08:45:17]
E021	13.96 hr (41.83%)	11.74 hr (51.13%)	[13/06/2032 16:02:08 to 14/06/2032 01:48:44] [15/06/2032 04:02:08 to 15/06/2032 05:59:52]
E022	12 hr (50%)	6.10 hr (74.58%)	[28/06/2032 10:46:14 to 28/06/2032 16:52:26]
E023	12 hr (50%)	6.15 hr (74.38%)	[15/07/2032 18:35:13 to 15/07/2032 21:55:22] [16/07/2032 03:46:34 to 16/07/2032 06:35:10]
E024	17.40 hr (27.50%)	17.40 hr (27.50%)	[30/07/2032 08:09:33 to 30/07/2032 20:09:33] [31/07/2032 22:10:22 to 01/08/2032 03:34:22]
E025	22.02 hr (8.25%)	22.02 hr (8.25%)	[17/08/2032 02:37:28 to 17/08/2032 14:37:25] [18/08/2032 14:37:28 to 19/08/2032 00:38:46]
E026	22.75 hr (5.21%)	22.75 hr (5.21%)	[31/08/2032 07:18:15 to 31/08/2032 19:18:12] [01/09/2032 19:18:15 to 02/09/2032 06:03:22]
E027	12.72 hr (47.00%)	12.72 hr (47.00%)	[27/05/2033 03:20:35 to 27/05/2033 04:03:35] [28/05/2033 04:03:37 to 28/05/2033 16:03:34]
E028	12 hr (50%)	9.14 hr (61.92%)	[15/06/2033 04:23:31 to 15/06/2033 13:31:59]
E029	12 hr (50%)	12 hr (50%)	[28/06/2033 22:56:26 to 29/06/2033 10:56:26]
E030	12 hr (50%)	7.85 hr (67.29%)	[16/07/2033 23:50:23 to 17/07/2033 07:41:11]
E031	12 hr (50%)	12 hr (50%)	[30/07/2033 18:41:43 to 31/07/2033 06:41:43]
E032	12 hr (50%)	12 hr (50%)	[13/08/2033 23:41:59 to 14/08/2033 11:41:59]
E033	12 hr (50%)	12 hr (50%)	[28/08/2033 04:37:56 to 28/08/2033 16:37:56]
E034	12 hr (50%)	9.89 hr (58.79%)	[11/09/2033 09:33:17 to 11/09/2033 19:27:16]
E035	12 hr (50%)	7.46 hr (68.92%)	[25/09/2033 14:28:08 to 25/09/2033 21:55:53]
E036	21.44 hr (10.67%)	15.85 hr (33.96%)	[08/10/2033 09:56:05 to 08/10/2033 11:06:33] [08/10/2033 11:21:07 to 08/10/2033 19:22:35] [09/10/2033 19:22:38 to 10/10/2033 00:30:12] [10/10/2033 05:51:18 to 10/10/2033 07:22:35]
E037	24 hr (0%)	16.81 hr (29.96%)	[22/10/2033 12:16:34 to 22/10/2033 12:54:54] [22/10/2033 14:27:31 to 23/10/2033 00:16:31] [24/10/2033 00:16:34 to 24/10/2033 03:14:43] [24/10/2033 08:53:20 to 24/10/2033 12:16:31]

Arc	TWs after Sun Exclusion (Loss %)	TWs after Jup. Exclusion (Loss %)	Time windows (Start to End)
E038	24 hr (0%)	17.75 hr (26.04%)	[05/11/2033 17:27:56 to 06/11/2033 05:06:18] [07/11/2033 05:06:21 to 07/11/2033 06:07:45] [07/11/2033 12:02:10 to 07/11/2033 17:06:18]
E039	24 hr (0%)	17.95 hr (25.21%)	[19/11/2033 20:55:16 to 20/11/2033 08:55:13] [21/11/2033 14:57:53 to 21/11/2033 20:55:13]
E040	19.62 hr (18.25%)	12.61 hr (47.46%)	[14/12/2033 07:40:41 to 14/12/2033 12:08:00] [14/12/2033 14:28:41 to 14/12/2033 19:40:38] [16/12/2033 00:03:32 to 16/12/2033 03:01:01]
E041	19.99 hr (16.71%)	12.42 hr (48.25%)	[08/01/2034 04:18:02 to 08/01/2034 05:35:44] [08/01/2034 07:50:45 to 08/01/2034 16:17:59] [10/01/2034 01:37:30 to 10/01/2034 04:17:59]
E042	19.77 hr (17.63%)	15.12 hr (37.00%)	[22/01/2034 10:31:44 to 22/01/2034 20:51:25] [24/01/2034 04:06:02 to 24/01/2034 08:52:25]
E043	19.69 hr (17.96%)	19.02 hr (20.75%)	[05/02/2034 13:36:04 to 06/02/2034 01:36:01] [07/02/2034 06:34:31 to 07/02/2034 13:36:02]
E044	20.02 hr (16.58%)	20.02 hr (16.58%)	[02/03/2034 10:15:10 to 02/03/2034 22:15:10] [04/03/2034 02:13:50 to 04/03/2034 10:15:10]
E045	20.4 hr (15.00%)	20.4 hr (15.00%)	[27/03/2034 06:47:07 to 27/03/2034 18:47:07] [28/03/2034 22:21:12 to 29/03/2034 06:47:07]
E046	20.24 hr (15.67%)	20.24 hr (15.67%)	[10/04/2034 11:29:12 to 10/04/2034 23:29:12] [12/04/2034 03:13:01 to 12/04/2034 11:29:12]
E047	20.30 hr (15.42%)	20.30 hr (15.42%)	[24/04/2034 16:05:42 to 25/04/2034 04:05:41] [26/04/2034 07:47:15 to 26/04/2034 16:05:41]
E048	21.04 hr (12.33%)	21.04 hr (12.33%)	[08/05/2034 20:58:59 to 09/05/2034 08:58:59] [10/05/2034 11:56:18 to 10/05/2034 20:58:59]
E049	21.99 hr (8.38%)	21.99 hr (8.38%)	[23/05/2034 01:51:26 to 23/05/2034 13:51:26] [24/05/2034 15:52:02 to 25/05/2034 01:51:26]
E050	22.97 hr (4.29%)	22.18 hr (7.58%)	[06/06/2034 06:47:48 to 06/06/2034 18:00:02] [07/06/2034 19:49:44 to 08/06/2034 06:47:46]
E051	23.73 hr (1.13%)	21.41 hr (10.79%)	[20/06/2034 11:43:34 to 20/06/2034 21:24:17] [22/06/2034 00:59:51 to 22/06/2034 11:43:31]
E052	24 hr (0%)	20.07 hr (16.38%)	[04/07/2034 16:40:12 to 05/07/2034 00:44:23] [06/07/2034 04:40:12 to 06/07/2034 16:40:09]
E053	20.05 hr (16.46%)	12.00 hr (50%)	[19/07/2034 09:23:11 to 19/07/2034 15:40:46] [20/07/2034 15:40:49 to 20/07/2034 21:20:29] [20/07/2034 23:40:54 to 20/07/2034 23:43:49]

Table S3: Observation Time Windows (TWs) for Europa Clipper Arcs

S4 Filter setup

In Table S4 are summarized all the parameters included in the estimation filter, together with their nominal and a priori values.

Spacecraft (local parameters)		
Parameter	Nominal Values and Specifications	A priori uncertainty
State	Initial states from CReMA 5.1 (JUICE) and 21F31 v4 (Europa Clipper)	Unconstrained
State offsets [X,Y,Z] *(Only for REVS)	[0,0,0] km	[100,100,100] m, from value assumed for Cassini by Tajeddine et al. [2013] ⁰
Antenna Phase Offsets	Nominal value: 0 m	1 m for X,Y,Z directions
SRP scale factor	Solar radiation pressure scaling factor set to 1.0	0.5
Range bias	Nominal value: 0 m	JUICE: 1 m Europa Clipper: 2 m
Empirical accelerations	Nominal value: 0 km/s ²	1.5×10^{-14} km/s ²
Galilean moons (global parameters)		
Parameter	Nominal Values and Specifications	A priori uncertainty
Satellites state	Epoch at 01-JAN-2033, initial state from JPL's jup380 (ftp://ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/pub/eph/satellites/bsp/jup380s.bsp)	Unconstrained
Galilean moons' GM	from JPL's jup380	Unconstrained
Europa's gravity harmonics coefficients	Quadrupole coefficients from Gomez Casajus et al. [2021] ¹ , higher terms simulated from Kaula's rule, $K = 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$. Estimated up to order and degree 15	Degree 2 unconstrained, higher terms Kaula's rule with $K = 10 \times 10^{-5}$
Ganymede's gravity harmonics coefficients	Gomez Casajus et al. [2022] ² , higher terms simulated from Kaula's rule, $K = 0.9 \times 10^{-5}$. Estimated up to order and degree 50	Degree 2 unconstrained, higher terms Kaula's rule with $K = 4.5 \times 10^{-5}$
Callisto's gravity harmonics coefficients	Quadrupole coefficients from Anderson et al. [2001] ³ , higher terms simulated from Kaula's rule, $K = 1.125 \times 10^{-5}$. Estimated up to order and degree 9	Degree 2 unconstrained, higher terms Kaula's rule with $K = 5.63 \times 10^{-5}$

Filter setup – continued from previous page

Tidal parameters	Estimated $Re(k_2)$ and $Im(k_2)$ for all the Galilean moons. $Re(k_2)$ from Lainey et al. [2009] ⁴ , Mazarico et al. [2023] ⁵ , Cappuccio et al. [2022] ⁶ . $Im(k_2)$ nominal value: 0	Unconstrained
Rotational state	Estimated libration amplitudes at orbital period and pole obliquity as right ascension and declination of rotational axis of Europa, Ganymede and Callisto	Libration amplitude unconstrained. R.A. and Dec = 0.5 deg
Jupiter (global parameters)		
Parameter	Nominal Values and Specifications	A priori uncertainty
State	With respect to Sun. Initial state from <i>DE440</i>	Unconstrained
GM and gravity harmonic coefficients	From Durante et al. [2020] ⁷ Estimated up to degree 6.	Durante et al. [2020] ⁷ sigmas $\times 100$
Tidal parameters	$Re(k_2)$ from Durante et al. [2020] ⁷ , $Im(k_2)$ nominal value: 0	Unconstrained
Rotational state	From Archinal et al. [2018] ⁸ . Assuming linear model for pole's right ascension, declination and prime meridian	Unconstrained

Table S4: Filter setup: estimated parameters with their own nominal values and a priori uncertainties

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S5 Noise

In this section are presented some important comments and details about the optical observables uncertainties introduced in the main paper.

S5.1 Limb-fitting Uncertainty

The formula used to find the limb-fitting uncertainty of an image taken at a given time instant is (Antreasian et al. [2005]):

$$\sigma_{lf}^2 = \sigma_{min}^2 + (C \cdot d_a)^2 \quad (S6)$$

For any time within the allowable TWs found, the apparent diameter d_a have been computed through the pinhole camera model (Equation S4). Figure S2 shows spacecraft-Io distances for both missions along all missions timelines. Distances involved vary within $(5.74e5 \div 2.69e6) \text{ km}$ for JUICE ARCS, $(3.87e5 \div 1.56e6) \text{ km}$ for Europa Clipper ARCS, $(3.91e5 \div 8.08e6) \text{ km}$ for JUICE REVS and $(4.12e5 \div 3.69e6) \text{ km}$ for Europa Clipper REVS. Exploiting the moon-spacecraft distances, the total apparent diameter on the detector of both cameras ranges between ~ 30 pixels (during JUICE's Rev001) and ~ 940 pixels (during Clipper's E009).

Figure S2: Camera-moon distances during all mission for JANUS (up) and NAC (down) cameras. Red dashed lines represent the C/A epochs of each mission

Regarding the two coefficients σ_{min} and C appearing in Equation S6, their values have been considered constant for any image. In order to find a realistic value for them, an average of the values found by Tajeddine et al. [2015] for Cassini and Saturnian moons (Table S5) has been considered. The values obtained are $\sigma_{min} = 0.0946$ and $C = 0.001082$.

Moon	σ_{min}	C
Tethys	0.087	0.00062
Dione	0.083	0.00052
Rhea	0.076	0.00077
Iapetus	0.086	0.0014
Phoebe	0.141	0.0021

Table S5: Fitted values for the weighting factor σ_{min} and scaling factor C for the five saturnian moons delineated by

In order to provide an order of magnitude for limb-fitting uncertainty, using the values defined for σ_{min} and C , in Table S6 are reported the minimum, maximum and mean values of σ_{lf} met along missions in different scenarios. It must be underlined that to retrieve a more interesting information these uncertainties should be multiplied by the pixel angular resolution to achieve the angular uncertainty in radians or degrees. In the last column of this Table the mean uncertainty in degrees is reported for each scenario.

Scenario	$\sigma_{lf,min}$ (pixels)	$\sigma_{lf,max}$ (pixels)	$\sigma_{lf,mean}$ (pixels)	$\sigma_{lf,mean}$ (degrees)
JUICE ARCS	0.136	0.468	0.197	1.692e-4
JUICE REVS	0.100	0.679	0.185	1.589e-4
Europa Clipper ARCS	0.269	1.022	0.441	2.527e-4
Europa Clipper REVS	0.134	0.962	0.236	1.352e-4

Table S6: Minimum, maximum and mean values of limb-fitting uncertainties for both missions in both scenarios used for optical observations selection

S5.2 Pointing Uncertainty

The pointing uncertainty plays an important role in the total uncertainty associated to an optical observable. Melman [2018] has modelled errors in the pointing correction using a theory for the accuracy of a star tracker by Liebe [1995]. Using this model, the uncertainty σ_p can be described as a function of the size of the field of view of the camera (FOV), the achievable sub-pixel precision of the stars' position $\sigma_{extraction}$, and the number of pixels and stars in the field of view, N_{pixels} and N_{FOV} , respectively:

$$\sigma_p = \frac{FOV \cdot \sigma_{extraction}}{N_{pixels} \cdot \sqrt{N_{FOV}}} \quad (S7)$$

where FOV is the Field of View of the camera in the dimension considered (x or y), $\sigma_{extraction}$ is the achievable sub-pixel precision of stars position, N_{pixels} is the number of pixels in the FOV and N_{FOV} is the number of stars in the FOV. The precision of the attitude determination from star trackers or from starfield matching improves with the number of well-resolved stars in the field of view. If the camera uses the stars in the image to determine or refine its pointing, the more stars in the FOV, the better the attitude estimation.

Assuming similar data-reduction techniques from Cassini, the value reported by Tajeddine et al. [2013] for $\sigma_{extraction}$ is 0.552. This is the value used in this analysis, assuming a similar imaging subsystem.

The crucial point is therefore to define a reasonable value for the number of stars within the field of view. Considering a rectangular FOV with area of approximately 2.22 deg² for JANUS, the stellar density model proposed by HNSKY gives an average of 9.28 stars/deg² for stars with

visual magnitude $V \leq 10$. This leads to a rough estimate: $N_{FOV} = 9.28 \cdot 2.22 \approx 20 \text{ stars}$. Reasoning in a similar way for NAC, a rough estimation of the number of sufficiently bright background stars in its FOV brings to a value of 26 stars . However, to be conservative, in the analysis a value of $N_{FOV} = 10$ has been considered for both missions, yielding to the following pointing uncertainties (constant since N_{FOV} has been considered constant):

- JUICE, $N_{FOV} = 10$: $\sigma_p \approx 1.495e - 4$ [deg]
- Europa Clipper, $N_{FOV} = 10$: $\sigma_p \approx 9.970e - 5$ [deg]

In Figure S3, the effect of N_{FOV} on the pointing uncertainty in pixels is shown for both JANUS and NAC cameras.

Figure S3: Effect of N_{FOV} on σ_p

As it can be seen, the behaviour of σ_p [pixels] is the same. Equation S7 contains FOV/N_{pixels} , which is the pixel angular resolution, and provides σ_p in degrees or radians (depending on the unit of measure of FOV). To obtain it in pixel units one should divide the equation by the pixel angular resolution, yielding simply to σ_p [pixels] = $\sigma_{extraction}/N_{FOV}$, which is independent on the camera. Plotting the same uncertainty in degrees one should see that the uncertainty of NAC camera is a bit smaller than the one of JANUS, since the latter has a bit larger pixel resolution.

S5.3 Spacecraft Position Uncertainty

The observed quantity retrievable by optical observables is not the absolute position of the observed object, but its relative position with respect to the spacecraft. The precision with which the position of a satellite can be measured ultimately depends on the uncertainties in determining the spacecraft's location. Following Tajeddine et al. [2013], the contribution of spacecraft position errors to the satellite's lateral position uncertainty (i.e., in a direction perpendicular to spacecraft's line-of-sight) can be quantified as:

$$\sigma_{sc} = \arcsin\left(\frac{\sigma_{S/C}}{D}\right), \quad (S8)$$

where D represents the distance between the spacecraft and the satellite, and $\sigma_{S/C}$ denotes the overall uncertainty in the spacecraft's position. To obtain the uncertainty in terms of pixels, the

result of Equation S8 should be divided by the pixel angular resolution of the camera used. In the case of this analysis, we must distinguish between the two scheduling scenarios considered:

- ARCS scenario: the spacecraft trajectory within arcs built around C/A of flybys is integrated using the radiometric measurements collected. From the results of radio-data only simulations, a suitable value for spacecraft position accuracy is around 5 *m*. Even using the smallest D met during mission ($3.87e5$ *km*, during Clipper's ARC E009, from Table ??), using Equation S8 the computed uncertainty in the position of Io is $\sigma_{sc} \approx 0.0013$ *pixels*, which is surely negligible with respect to the other two uncertainties (two orders of magnitude smaller).
- REVS scenario: along revolutions we cannot integrate the trajectory, because the arc is too long, in the middle there are maneuvers, so the trajectory would diverge after a short. The reference trajectory is used. In order to take into account the uncertainty in its position, for any observation time an offset has been introduced in its trajectory, estimated by the filter.

S6 Correlations Model

In this section it is presented the complete method used for the estimation of the correlation between two optical observables.

Two images are considered correlated when they are very similar and therefore carry essentially the same information; conversely, they are considered uncorrelated when they are sufficiently dissimilar. For each pair of images acquired at different times we compute a correlation coefficient ρ , which by definition ranges from 0 (completely uncorrelated) to 1 (fully correlated). Naturally, the correlation of an image with itself equals 1.

The approximated model introduced consider two contributions forming the total correlation ρ_{tot} :

- Limb-fitting correlation (ρ_{lf}): this contribution is dependent on the differences in phase angle and apparent diameter between the two images, which are important parameters influencing the limb-fitting procedure (this is the reason of the name).

Equation S9 express the correlation coming from the difference in the phase angle (φ):

$$\rho_{\varphi} = \left(\frac{1 + \cos(\Delta\varphi)}{2} \right)^p, \quad (\text{S9})$$

where $\Delta\varphi$ is the difference between the phase angles computed at two different observation times (i.e., when the images are taken), and p is a free parameter introduced to add flexibility in modelling the correlation. Figure S4 shows the behaviour of ρ_{φ} as $\Delta\varphi$ varies from 0° to 360° , for different values of p . The value chosen for p in the analysis is 8.

Figure S4: Correlation coming from the difference in phase angle between two hypothetical images

Equation S10 express the correlation coming from the difference in the apparent diameter of the moon (i.e., its distance from the camera):

$$\rho_d = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\Delta d_{rel}}{d_0}\right)^2\right) \quad (\text{S10})$$

where d_0 is a free parameter to adjust the dependency (chosen to be $d_0 = 0.1$) and Δd_{rel} is the relative difference of apparent diameter:

$$\Delta d_{rel} = \frac{|d_2 - d_1|}{\bar{D}} \quad (\text{S11})$$

with \bar{D} is the mean apparent diameter between the two images:

$$\bar{D} = \frac{d_1 + d_2}{2} \quad (\text{S12})$$

In Figure S5 it is shown the behaviour of ρ_d varying Δd_{rel} , for different values of d_0 . As done for p coefficient in the case of phase angle correlation, also in this case it is possible to change d_0 value to achieve the desired and most realistic behaviour of the correlation. In the analysis, a value of $d_0 = 0.1$ has been used.

Figure S5: Correlation coming from the difference in apparent diameter between two hypothetical images

The limb-fitting uncertainty is then defined as $\rho_{lf} = \omega\rho_\varphi + (1-\omega)\rho_d$, where ω is introduced as weight of the two correlation contributions. In this analysis it has been used $\omega = 0.5$.

- Pointing Correlation (ρ_p): this contribution quantifies the difference in the portion of sky captured by the camera between two images (i.e., the difference in the camera pointing). This correlation has been parametrized through the portion of background sky overlapping between two images, going linearly from 0 when the overlapping region captured is null to 1 when two images represent the same portion of sky (Figure S6).

Figure S6: Scheme of two images taken within a generic arc having a portion of FOV overlapped

The formula used is:

$$\rho_p = \max\left(0, 1 - \left(\frac{\theta_{ij}}{FOV}\right)\right), \quad (\text{S13})$$

where θ_{ij} is the angular separation between the line-of-sight of two photos within a given arc, computed as the angle between lines-of-sight spacecraft-Io at two time instants (i.e., assuming that z axis of camera always points perfectly towards Io at image acquisition times).

The behaviour of the correlation varying this angle is showed in Figure S7. When the separation reaches $\theta_{ij} = 2 \cdot FOV/2 = FOV$, the two images are completely decorrelated ($\rho_p = 0$) from the point of view of pointing, since the two portions of sky imaged are not overlapping. In Figure S7 FOV is referred to JANUS camera and as FOV has been taken the larger component of asymmetric camera FOV to ensure the non-overlapping condition. In this case, since a simple linear approach is adopted, no degrees of freedom are introduced.

Figure S7: Graph of pointing correlation varying angular separation between two images for JANUS ($FOV_x = 1.72$)

The total correlation can be computed from the two contributions introduced. Following some statistic reasoning, the total correlation between two images ($\rho_{i,j}$) can be computed as:

- Define $X_i = L_i + P_i$ and $X_j = L_j + P_j$ as the total error of two images, formed by limb-fitting error (L) and pointing one (P).
- Denoting $\sigma_{X,i}^2 = E[X_i^2]$, then one can obtain the following uncertainties formulations:

$$\sigma_{X,i}^2 = \sigma_{lf,i}^2 + \sigma_{p,i}^2 ; \sigma_{X,j}^2 = \sigma_{lf,j}^2 + \sigma_{p,j}^2 \quad (S14)$$

where, obviously, $\sigma_{lf}^2 = E[L^2]$ and $\sigma_p^2 = E[P^2]$.

- Let's denote the limb-fitting correlation and the pointing correlations as functions of the covariances:

$$\rho_{lf} = \frac{cov(L_i, L_j)}{\sigma_{lf,i}\sigma_{lf,j}} ; \rho_p = \frac{cov(P_i, P_j)}{\sigma_{p,i}\sigma_{p,j}} \quad (S15)$$

- The total correlation between images i and j comes from the covariance between X_i and X_j :

$$\begin{aligned} cov(X_i, X_j) &= cov(L_i + P_i, L_j + P_j) = \\ &= cov(L_i, L_j) + cov(L_i, P_j) + cov(L_j, P_i) + cov(P_i, P_j) = \\ &= cov(L_i, L_j) + cov(P_i, P_j), \end{aligned} \quad (S16)$$

assuming independence between crossed limb-fitting and pointing.

- Remembering the correlation formula (Eq. S15), we can compute:

$$\text{cov}(X_i, X_j) = \rho_{lf} \sigma_{lf,i} \sigma_{lf,j} + \rho_p \sigma_{p,i} \sigma_{p,j} \quad (\text{S17})$$

- Compute $\sigma_{X,i} \sigma_{X,j}$ from Eq. S14. Under linear assumption:

$$\sigma_{X,i} \sigma_{X,j} = \sigma_{lf,i} \sigma_{lf,j} + \sigma_{p,i} \sigma_{p,j} \quad (\text{S18})$$

- Finally it can be computed:

$$\rho_{i,j} = \frac{\text{cov}(X_i, X_j)}{\sigma_{X,i} \sigma_{X,j}} = \frac{\rho_{lf} \cdot \sigma_{lf,i} \sigma_{lf,j} + \rho_p \cdot \sigma_{p,i} \sigma_{p,j}}{\sigma_{lf,i} \sigma_{lf,j} + \sigma_{p,i} \sigma_{p,j}}, \quad (\text{S19})$$

where ρ_{lf} and ρ_p are, respectively, the limb-fitting and the pointing correlation, while σ_{lf} and σ_p are, respectively, the limb-fitting uncertainty and the pointing uncertainty computed at given instant time with the formulas introduced in Section S5. The subscripts i and j indicates two different instant times (i.e. images).

In this formula the weights of the two correlations are the corresponding uncertainties: larger pointing uncertainties, for example, means the pointing correlation is more important between images.

Such computation allows for the definition of the correlation matrices in Figure S8. In particular, one total correlation matrix has been computed for each ARC/REV of the two missions.

Figure S8: Example of three correlation matrices (from left to right: limb-fitting correlation, pointing correlation and total correlation) for an hypothetical set of imaging instants defined within C05 JUICE's arc

S7 Scheduling Strategies Derivation

The procedure followed for the observation epochs selection is the following:

1. Choice of strategy to test: ARCS or REVS;
2. Application of constraints defined and, for each ARC/REV, identification of allowable time windows (TWs) for optical observations;
3. For each ARC/REV: discretization of the TWs (with a certain timestep), obtaining a bundle of subsequent instants;
4. Computation of mutual correlation between images taken at any couple of instants within the bundle (following the computation explained in Section S6). The output of this step is a total correlation matrix for each ARC/REV.

5. Extraction of the maximum number of images/observation instants with mutual correlation under a certain threshold (γ_{max}). This procedure is known as MIS (Maximum independent set) problem. Each observable (or image) is represented as a node in a graph G . An edge is added between two nodes i and j if the correlation between the corresponding observables exceeds a predefined threshold (in this case, $\rho_{i,j} \geq \gamma_{max}$). Because finding the true maximum independent set is an NP-hard problem, the exact solution becomes computationally expensive for large graphs. For this reason the NetworkX function *maximum_independent_set*(G) uses a greedy heuristic algorithm to find the largest subset of nodes that are not connected by any edge in G .

In the framework of this project, it has been decided to set $\gamma_{max} = 0.35$, meaning that, within a given arc or revolution, the maximum set of images with mutual correlation below 0.35 has been considered for the scheduling strategy.

Furthermore, the timestep determining the discretization density of the TWs can be chosen: a larger timestep implies a coarser discretization and forces the observation times of final set to be more separated in time, fixing a minimum time interval between them. In the cases relative to the ARCS scenario, the timestep used for the discretization is 5 minutes, since during flybys scientific experiments are more likely to be performed and we don't have problems having closer observation times. On the other hand, for the REVS scenario, the timestep has been imposed equal to 24 hours, since far from flybys scientific experiments as optical observations can't be too frequent, due to logistic considerations.

Following this procedure, different scheduling strategies have been found for the different scenarios.

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